

EFFECT OF AEROBIC DANCE TRAINING ON FLEXIBILITY AMONG COLLEGE WOMEN STUDENTS

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Abstract:

In this context, the investigator made an attempt to investigate the effect of aerobic dance training on flexibility among college women students. To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty students were randomly selected as subjects from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur. The age of the subjects were ranged from 18 to 21 years. The subjects selected for this study were divided into two groups of fifteen subjects each. The experimental group I underwent aerobic dance training and group II acted as a control group. The subjects were exposed to a aerobic dance training programme for six weeks. The training programmes were organized in a progressive manner. The obtained data from the experimental and control groups initial and final readings were statistically analyzed with 't' test. The level of confidence which was fixed at 0.05 levels was considered as an appropriate one for this study. It was observed that the experimental group has significantly improved the flexibility.

Key Words: Aerobic Dance Training, Flexibility, Women Students

Introduction:

Aerobic exercise and fitness can be contrasted with anaerobic exercise, of which strength training and weight training are the most salient examples. The two types of exercise differ by the duration and intensity of muscular contractions involved, as well as by how energy is generated within the muscle. Initially during aerobic exercise, glycogen is broken down to produce glucose, but in its absence, fat metabolism is initiated instead. The latter is a slow process, and is accompanied by a decline in performance level. The switch to fat as fuel is a major cause of what marathon runner's call "hitting the wall". Anaerobic exercise, in contrast, refers to the initial phase of exercise, or any short burst of intense exertion, in which the glycogen or sugar is consumed without oxygen, and is a far less efficient process. Operating an aerobically, an untrained 400 meter sprinter may "hit the wall" short of the full distance (Gary et al. 2017).

Methodology:

In this context, the investigator made an attempt to investigate the effect of aerobic dance training on flexibility among college women students. To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty students were randomly selected as subjects from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur. The age of the subjects were ranged from 18 to 21 years. The subjects selected for this study were divided into two groups of fifteen subjects each. The experimental group I underwent aerobic dance training and group II acted as a control group. The subjects were exposed to a aerobic dance training programme for six weeks. The training programmes were organized in a progressive manner. The obtained data from the experimental and control groups initial and final readings were statistically analyzed with 't' test. The level of confidence which was fixed at 0.05 levels was considered as an appropriate one for this study.

Results:

Table 1: Computation of 't' Ratio of the Flexibility Experimental Group

S.No	Name of the Test	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean Difference	σDM	't' value
1	Pre-Test	33.53	1.10	4.60	0.58	3.94*
2	Post-Test	38.13	1.68			

Required Table values for 14 degrees of freedom 2.14 at 0.05 level

It is observed from the table I that there is significant difference on flexibility. It is seen that the mean of the pre-test 33.53 and post-test 38.13 the standard deviation of the pre-test 1.10 and post-test 1.68 obtained 't' ratio is 3.94. The table value of 't' ratio is 2.14 the obtained 't' ratio is higher than the table value hence the obtained 't' ratio is significant at 0.05 level confidence.

Table 2: Computation of 't' Ratio of the Flexibility Control Group

S.No	Name of the Test	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean Difference	σDM	't' value
1	Pre-Test	33.22	1.01	0.24	0.96	0.77
2	Post-Test	33.46	1.32			

Required Table values for 14 degrees of freedom 2.14 at 0.05 level

It is observed from the table II that there is no significant difference on flexibility. It is seen that the mean of the pre-test 33.22 and post-test 33.46 the standard deviation of the pre-test 1.01 and post-test 1.32

obtained 't' ratio is 0.77. The table value of 't' ratio is 2.14 the obtained 't' ratio is less than the table value hence the obtained 't' ratio is no significant at 0.05 level confidence.

Figure 1: Bar Diagram Showing the Mean Difference of Pre-Test and Post Test of Experimental and Control Group in Flexibility

Conclusion:

It was observed that the experimental group has significantly improved the flexibility.

References:

1. Anek, A., Kanungsukasem, V. & Bunyaratavej, N. (2015). Effects of Aerobic Step Combined with Resistance Training on Biochemical Bone Markers, Health-Related Physical Fitness and Balance in Working Women. *J Med Assoc Thai*. 2015 Sep; 98 Suppl 8:S42-51.
2. Chen, W.H., Wu, H.J., Lo, S.L., Chen, H., Yang, W.W., Huang, C.F. & Liu, C. (2018). Eight-week battle rope training improves multiple physical fitness dimensions and shooting accuracy in collegiate basketball players. *J Strength Cond Res* 32(10): 2715–2724.
3. Eduardo, J. A. M., Santos Manuel A. & Janeira, A. S. (2008). Effects of Complex Training on Explosive Strength in Adolescent Male Basketball Players. *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*. 22(3)/903–909.
4. Gary S. Goldfield, Glen P. Kenny, Angela S. Alberga, Heather E. Tulloch, Steve Doucette, Jameason D. Cameron & Ronald J. Sigal (2017). Effects of aerobic or resistance training or both on health-related quality of life in youth with obesity: the HEARTY Trial. *Applied Physiology, Nutrition, and Metabolism*, 42(4): 361-370.
5. Goldfield, G. S., Kenny, G. P., Alberga, A. S., Prud'homme, D., Hadjiyannakis, S., Gougeon, R., Sigal, R. J. (2015). Effects of aerobic training, resistance training, or both on psychological health in adolescents with obesity: The Hearty randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 83(6), 1123-1135.
6. Guo Siqiang (2018). Experimental study of aerobic exercise on the weight loss effect of obese female college students. *Biomedical Research*, 193-S196.
7. Harsh Patel, Hassan Alkhawam, Raef Madanieh, Niel Shah, Constantine E Kosmas & Timothy J Vittorio (2017). Aerobic vs anaerobic exercise training effects on the cardiovascular system. *World J Cardiol*. 26; 9(2): 134–138.
8. Suresh, Kumar M. (2017). Influence of Yoga Practices on Blood Pressure among Rural College Girls. *Star International Research Journal*, 5, 1(3).
9. C. A. Vijayarani, Dr. V. Vallimurugan & M. Suresh Kumar (2012). Influence of Yogic Practices on Selected Physiological and Psychological Variables of Adolescent Boys. *Recent Research in Science and Technology*. 3,1.
10. Eswaramoorthy, A. & Suresh Kumar, M. (2020). Effect of yogic practices and aerobic training on flexibility among physical education students. *Purakala*, 31, 8, 417-420.
11. Suresh, Kumar M. (2020). Investigation of the Changes on Selected Physical Fitness Parameters in Response to SAQ Training among College Women Students. *Alochana Chakra Journal*, 9, 4, 5121-5124.